

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN LEARNING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

Motivation plays a very important and significant role in learning English as a foreign language (EFL) as it has a significant impact on students' persistence, engagement and academic success. This study aims to investigate the importance of motivation in learning English as a foreign language and how different forms of motivation affect students' language learning abilities. The study is based on a theoretical analysis of current research conducted by local and global researchers in the fields of second language learning and educational psychology. This study examines the critical role of motivation in the successful acquisition of English as a foreign language (EFL). Rather than simply describing established motivation theories (e.g., intrinsic/extrinsic), this study examines how these motivational forces are manifested in students' behavior and academic performance. The findings show a strong relationship between high motivation and increased language proficiency, suggesting that students with intrinsic or strategic motivation are more deeply engaged in the learning process, resulting in improved skills and higher grades.

Key words: English as a foreign language, motivation, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, motivational strategies, teachers' role

INTRODUCTION

Motivation is main factor of today's education system, as it is one of the key psychological elements that direct, activate and sustain learners' educational activities. In modern educational settings, motivation increases learners' desire to acquire knowledge. It also helps develop interest in learning and supports independent and creative thinking, which leads to academic success. According to Cook (2000), age, personality, and motivation are the main factors influencing second language learning, among which motivation is considered the most important (Cook, 2000; Rashed, 2000). As an addition to the above idea, motivation is a key element of learning but language learning is more successful for students with high motivation (Dörnyei & Csizer, 1998). Despite the apparent value of motivation and its recognition in various contexts, students in foreign language classes continue to have difficulty maintaining their enthusiasm for the task. As a result, students start to fall behind because they lose interest. Despite the widespread and recognized importance of motivation, many students still struggle to maintain interest and motivation in learning a foreign language. In secondary and high school students still think that English is a tough subject, and they seem uninterested in acquiring English in the learning spaces. Although it cannot be generalized that their lack of English proficiency is related to their low motivation, it does indicate that students' motivation

contributes to their English language competence. A study by Midraj et al. (2008) on the relationship between motivation and students' achievement indicates positive correlation in which students with high motivation tend to have better achievement in learning language. Learning English as a foreign language is a multi-stage continuous cognitive process. The implementation of this process involves several important factors. The first of these is, of course, motivation. It is considered as a set of internal and external forces of a student or learner, which are one of the main factors that encourage them to learn a language. A learner's enthusiasm, desire and aspiration for self-development are all included in intrinsic motivation. Encouragement, praise, various awards and social pressure in the learning process cause extrinsic motivation. In language learning, the learner's personal view of the language and success are revealed through motivation. Only when a person takes responsibility for his life can he have an internal locus of control and develop a self-motivating character, and if he places responsibility on others, that is, on those around him and on circumstances outside himself, he will have an external locus of control. To achieve an internal locus of control that can motivate him, one must give up the security of making excuses and be willing to take responsibility for all his decisions and actions.

Extrinsically motivated behavior is performed to receive rewards from outside and outside of himself. In this case, a person can only achieve short-term motivation. (Badenjkı & Kuprina, 2023) However, in many cases, the interaction of internal and external factors in language learning is considered to be different. "Research shows that individuals who learn a language with intrinsic motivation are more likely to have a sustained interest in the language, long-term acquisition, and self-development. For example, the Self-Determination Theory proposed that justifies the sustainable development of intrinsic motivation in language learning in conditions that provide autonomy, competence, and social relevance (Deci & Ryan, 2000, p. 68; Shomamatova, 2020, p. 115). The importance of motivation in learning a second and foreign language suggests that it needs to be analyzed in depth not only from a theoretical but also from a practical perspective. Although previous studies have highlighted the impact of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on student achievement, this impact largely depends on the motivational strategies used in the lesson. Therefore, the next section will consider effective motivational strategies in teaching English as a foreign language. Motivation strategy is an important pedagogical approach that serves to increase students' interest in learning and activity in the educational process. In particular, the correct selection and use of motivation strategies in the process of learning English as a foreign language directly affects the level of language acquisition and academic success of students. When motivation strategies are organized taking into account the internal needs of students and external motivating factors, the educational process is more effective. Strategies aimed at developing internal motivation support students' personal interest, independent thinking and striving for self-development. Such approaches serve to give students freedom in the learning process, take into account their individual interests and strengthen their need to acquire knowledge through real-life tasks. As a result, students and learners begin to view language not only as a duty, but also as a means of personal development. At the same time, extrinsic motivation approaches still shape how students grow. Praise, approval, recognition, and feedback can boost engagement among those who are less confident in the lesson process. However, relying solely on external motivation cannot provide

long-term results, since the process of sustainable and deep learning is mainly associated with internal motivation.

The effectiveness of motivational strategies largely depends on the teacher's professional skills and the classroom environment, and a positive, supportive and error-tolerant educational environment significantly improves students' attitude to learning. The teacher's attitude towards students, methods of motivating them and forms of organizing the lesson increase students' interest in learning English and have a positive impact on the development of their language competence. In general, an important pedagogical factor in the learning process is manifested through the systematic introduction of motivational strategies into the educational process, making students' English learning more effective, developing their independent learning skills, and ensuring their academic success. As mentioned above, how well motivational strategies work largely depends on the teacher, that is, the main person who helps students become interested in learning and be active. It is the teacher's task to guide students in the right direction, to be able to correctly direct motivational factors, to create a supportive learning environment, and to help students be active. Therefore, the next section will discuss in detail the role of teachers and the interaction of the classroom environment on student motivation. The teacher is a person who always guide students to be motivated. The teacher's pedagogical approach, attitude, and interaction with students during the lesson directly affect their interest and activity in learning English. In many cases, students' indifference or lack of interest in the lesson may be viewed learning and the poor social organization of the classroom. The teacher's attitudes (positiveness and encouragement) are another part that can help students to have more confidence and interact actively in lesson. In a nurturing classroom, the students receive an experience that is similar where thoughts can be shared, questions asked and learning extended without fear of making mistakes. As a result, the language learning process becomes more interesting and serves to increase student activity. In an environment where a correct, encouraging attitude towards mistakes is established, students further develop their communicative skills and begin to perceive language as a real means of communication. Notably, students begin to see value when feedback feels direct but fair-delivered without delay, carefully crafted. Such feedback shifts their perspective on learning, quietly but consistently motivating action. Here, teaching doesn't stop at delivering facts; it extends to providing encouragement, where the constant presence of one person creates a space for others to lean on. When responses feel genuine rather than robotic, a roomful of attentiveness is more likely. When motivation flows through someone who feels it, it spreads without fanfare. Passion is deepened not by spectacle but by moments when the student feels seen. Success in language is rooted in part because feedback does a very slow, consistent, silent, but important job.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the past few years, EFL has acquired more and more relevance as a consequence of several reasons, including globalization and international communication and academic mobility. English is popular in the education, science and technology fields, this fact shows how important English to students around the world. Nevertheless, numerous EFL learners encounter challenges in studying English efficiently, and one of the most important factors influencing their achievement is motivation. According to Harmer (2007, p. 98) about motivation, motivation is the external reflection of an internal action that urges a person to do

something. Also, Winke (2005, p. 4) advances Gardner's idea that motivation is based on a social model of language acquisition. According to this model, the motivation to learn a foreign language is interpreted as a complex and integrated system that includes the desire to learn, active actions aimed at its implementation, and a positive attitude towards language learning (Gardner, 1985; Winke, 2005, p. 4). This may mean that the motivation to learn a foreign language is different from other types of motivation.

In terms of motivation categorization, Dörnyei (1994, p. 275) argues that one of the most general and well-known distinctive features of motivation theories is that “motivation can be categorized into intrinsic and extrinsic motivation”. This classification, according to Noels et al. (2003), is based on Self-determination Theory. In that theory, intrinsic motivation refers to “motivation to engage in an activity because it is enjoyable and satisfying to do” (Noels et al., 2003, p. 38). From the theory, it can be concluded that intrinsic motivation comes from the inner aspects of individual learners. Meanwhile, extrinsic motivation comes from external sides of the learners. The extrinsic motivation that can be in forms of money, prizes, grades, and even punishment (Brown, 2007). In general, both extrinsic and intrinsic motivation are crucial in the success of learners in all levels of their education (Susanto, 2018).

In second or foreign language learning, motivation is one of the important factors that contributes to the success of learning languages (Dörnyei & Csizer, 1998). Additionally, Wang (2006, p. 32) says that “motivation is an important affective variable in second language acquisition and it has correlation with second language achievement and proficiency”. This indicates that even though motivation is not the only factor which contributes to the achievement of the language, it is a crucial factor in learning a language. Similarly, Dörnyei (1994, p. 273) argues that motivation is “one of determinants of second or foreign language learning achievement”. From Wang’s and Dörnyei’s point of views, it is clear that motivation is an important factor in language learning and influences students’ achievement in their second or foreign language learning. Motivation is an important factor in learning a foreign language and has been shown to significantly influence student success and achievement. Understanding the true nature of motivation and its types is crucial to explaining the differences in student outcomes during and after language learning.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a **quantitative research method** to determine the role of motivation in learning English as a foreign language. Quantitative research appeared in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. During the 20th century, survey (questionnaire), test, and experimental methods were developed, which made it possible to collect systematic and objective information from many participants. This method can collect and include data that can be measured, counted, and analyzed statistically, such as yes/no responses, percentages, or numerical ratings of participants which can be analyzed statistically. In this study, the quantitative research method was chosen not qualitative because it is possible to obtain accurate and quantifiable data from a large number of students through this method. due to these facilities, the study was conducted without problems. Students' motivation was analyzed by means of numbers and percentages with the help of closed questions in the form of a questionnaire. This made it possible to compare internal and external motivation and draw a general conclusion. Therefore, the quantitative method was found to be the most appropriate method for the purpose of the research. To collect essential data, one of the most popular tools

– online survey – was conducted among 35 participants. All participants in this survey were students between the ages of 18-22 and studying at the Bachelor's level. In addition to their age, gender and academic level. The main objective of the study was to study students' interest in learning English, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation factors, as well as the influence of the teacher's role and classroom environment on their motivation. The survey consisted of 10 closed-ended questions, which were aimed at determining the level of interest of students in English, sources of motivation, classroom activity, teacher attitude, feedback, and the impact of motivational methods. Below given some the survey questions.

-How interested are you in learning English?

-What motivates you most to learn English?

-Which classroom activities motivate you to learn English?

-Do you feel confident expressing yourself in class (asking questions, sharing opinions)

-How does your teacher's attitude affect your motivation learn English?

-Does feedback and encouragement from your teacher increase your interest in learning English

-How does your intrinsic motivation (personal interest, desire for self-development) affect your English learning success?

-How does is external motivation (grades, awards, social encouragement) in encouraging you to learn English?

The questionnaire questions were structured on a Likert scale and respondents were given the opportunity to choose the most appropriate option from several options. The data obtained were processed using the descriptive analysis method and analyzed in the form of percentages and overall indicators.

RESULTS

This section presents the results of the study, which aimed to investigate the role of motivation in learning English as a foreign language. According to the survey results, the level of interest in learning English among students was determined through percentages. Based on the analysis of the responses, percentages were recorded among students on the level of interest in learning English and types of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Furthermore, the results showed that responses related to teacher attitude, encouraging feedback, and classroom environment were expressed in percentages. According to the result (Table 1), female and male students showed different percentages in terms of motivation types, experiences in the classroom, and attitudes towards the teacher factor.

Table 1. Survey questions and

Age	Gender	Degree	Questions	Answers
18-22	Female	Bachelor's students	How interested are you in learning English?	Very interested
18-22	Female	Bachelor's students	Motivation type	Personal interest (intrinsic)
18-22	Female	Bachelor's students	Learning for enjoyment?	Yes
18-22	Female	Bachelor's students	Learning for grades / rewards?	Yes

18-22	Female	Bachelor's students	Classroom activities motivating most	Group work / discussions
18-22	Female	Bachelor's students	Confidence expressing in class	Confident
18-22	Male	Bachelor's students	Teacher's attitude effect	Positively
18-22	Male	Bachelor's students	Feedback / encouragement effect	Increases
18-22	Male	Bachelor's students	Intrinsic motivation effect	Positively
18-22	Male	Bachelor's students	Extrinsic motivation effectiveness	Effective
18-22	Male	Bachelor's students	Difficulty of learning	Neutral
18-22	Male	Bachelor's students	What could increase motivation?	Interactive lessons

The table provides information on the motivation, English learning habits, and classroom experiences of undergraduate students aged 18–22. In general, there are many female students who are very interested in learning English, 65.9% of them (29 people) expressed a high interest. In the question about the type of motivation, half of female students (50%, 22 people) connected their studies with personal interest (internal). On the motivation side, 80% (28 students) said they learn English for fun, and 20% (7 students) said they learn it for grades or other extrinsic rewards. Among classroom activities, 31.8% (14 students) found group work and discussions to be the most stimulating, and 38.6% (17 students) noted that female students can confidently express their opinions during class. 45.5% of male students (20 students) stated that the teacher's response has a positive effect on motivation, 36.4% (16 students) stated that feedback and encouragement rise motivation. 45.5% of men (20 students) believed that internal motivation has a positive effect, and 40.9% (18 students) considered external motivation to be effective. Regarding learning difficulty, the majority of male students (56.8%, 25 students) chose a neutral answer. Finally, only 8.6% (3 people) believed that interactive lessons can increase motivation. As a result of the data show that motivation among female students is mainly related to intrinsic motivation and enjoyment of learning, while male students are influenced by teacher and motivational strategies, group work, feedback and classroom activities play an important role in increasing motivation for all students.

Graph 1. Survey question examples

Research question was (Graph 2) “How does intrinsic motivation (personal interest and desire for self-development) affect students’ success in learning English?” The results are presented in Table 1, which the number and percentage of students who chose each response option. From the table, the largest group of students (16; 45.5%) reported that intrinsic motivation had a positive effect on the results of learning English. At the same time, 6 students (15.9%) rated this effect as very positive. 13 students (36.4%) considered the effect neutral. Only 1 student (2.3%) indicated that this effect was slightly negative, and no one noted that it had no effect at all. These results indicate that intrinsic motivation among students - personal interest and the desire to develop oneself - has a positive effect on the successful learning of English for most people.

Graph 2. Examples of results after survey.

The next research question was (Graph 3) “To what extent do extrinsic motivation (grades, rewards, social support) affect English learning?” The responses are shown in Table 3, with the number and percentage of students for each option. As can be seen from the table, the majority of students (14; 40.9%) rated extrinsic motivation as effective, while 14 students

(40.9%) considered this effect to be neutral. 4 students (11.4%) considered this effect to be very effective, and 2 students (4.5%) considered it to be somewhat effective. Only 1 student (2.3%) considered this motivation not effective at all. These results indicate that extrinsic motivation and rewards have different effects on student motivation, and also indicate that there are significant differences in terms of their effectiveness.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study show that intrinsic motivation (personal interest and desire for self-development) among students has a significant impact on English language learning success. Research shows that only when students take responsibility for their own lives can they develop an internal locus of control and become self-motivated. If they place responsibility on others or external circumstances, they have an external locus of control, and motivation is only short-lived. Therefore, to develop intrinsic motivation, students must be willing to abandon the security of making excuses and take responsibility for all their decisions and actions in learning English (Badenjki & Kuprina, 2023). The largest group in the Result section (16, 45.5%) reported that intrinsic motivation had a positive impact, while 6 students (15.9%) rated this impact as very positive. These findings are consistent with Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000) and previously cited theories, intrinsic motivation helps to strengthen in conditions that provide personal independence, competence, and social significance and allows them to continue the learning process effectively. Therefore, it is confirmed that high intrinsic motivation among students is associated with their active participation and desire for self-development. In term of extrinsic motivation (grades, rewards, social support) is also important, but it is expressed differently among students. According to the results of the Results section, 14 students (40.9%) rated extrinsic motivation as effective, while another 14 students (40.9%) rated it as neutral. This result is consistent with Brown (2007) and Susanto (2018), who argue that extrinsic motivation and rewards can help increase student motivation in a number of ways, but that intrinsic motivation plays a key role in long-term and deep learning. The results also show gender differences. Female students' motivation in the learning process is mainly related to intrinsic motivation and enjoyment of learning, while male students are influenced by teacher attitudes, feedback, group work, and classroom activities. These findings, in line with the theories of Harmer (2007) and Dörnyei (1994), confirm that motivational strategies and teacher approaches have a significant impact on student performance and interest in learning. These indicators show that female students learn more through their own intrinsic motivation than male students, but it is known that the influence of the teacher increases the motivation to learn more in male students. There are also unexpected findings from this study. The only 3 (8.6%) students who chose the answer that interactive lessons rise motivation. That can be related to the teacher's approach, the content of the lesson, or the students' previous experience. Also, the neutral answer regarding the difficulty of learning was chosen by the majority of male students (56.8%), which is evidence of individual differences in the learning process and the effectiveness of motivational strategies in the lesson.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that intrinsic motivation, which is students' personal interest and desire to develop themselves, has the strongest positive impact on learning English as a foreign language, with the majority of students rating its impact as positive or very positive. Extrinsic

motivation, including grades, rewards and social incentives, can stimulate short-term activity, but in most cases, its neutral assessment shows that it is limited in ensuring deep and long-term learning. The results of the study also reveal gender differences: female students rely mainly on intrinsic motivation, while male students are more influenced by the teacher's attitude, feedback and interactive lesson activities. The role of the teacher is very important, and a supportive, error-tolerant learning environment and timely constructive feedback significantly increase students' motivation and self-confidence. Therefore, to ensure the best results in the learning process, it is important to organize tasks in a way that serves to provide students with independence, significance and personal development, and to stimulate intrinsic motivation. Extrinsic motivation should only be used as an additional factor to intrinsic motivation, as it is short-term or medium-term. It should not be used as the main source of motivation, but as a key tool in the learning process. Learning English as a foreign language requires a lot of time and effort. In addition, improving teachers' pedagogical skills, providing positive and constructive feedback, creating a supportive and learner-centered learning environment, and the introduction of interactive and group activities into the learning process helps to increase student motivation. Teachers need to develop effective skills in motivational strategies to maintain students' interest in the lesson and increase their success in learning English as a foreign language.

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